

Paper 20

**A CORRELATIVE STUDY OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE TEACHER TRAINEES**

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to see the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance among the teacher trainees based on their locality as well as their stream (Science/Arts) of study. Emotional intelligence was established as key predictor variable in the success of teacher trainees. For academic performance in the present study, the students' term end results were used to obtain pertinent and precise information. The sample consisted of 52 students (20 Science and 32 Arts stream) selected from Srinivas College of Education, Srinivas University, Mangaluru by using simple random sampling technique, emotional intelligence inventory was developed by Dr. S.K. Mangal and Mrs. Shubhra Mangal. In this inventory there are total 100 items and it is divided into four areas (Intra-personal management, interpersonal management, intrapersonal awareness and interpersonal awareness). Mean, SD, t-value and Pearson's product movement coefficient of correlation methods were used for data analysis. The result reveals that there is a relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance as well as with their background in terms of their locality and stream of study (Science/Arts).

1.0.0 Introduction

Emotional intelligence (otherwise known as **emotional quotient** or EQ) is the ability to understand, use, and manage one's own **emotions** in positive ways to relieve stress, communicate effectively, empathize with others, overcome challenges and defuse conflict.

Emotional intelligence is commonly defined by four attributes:

1. **Self-management** – One is able to control impulsive feelings and behaviors, manage emotions in healthy ways, take initiative, follow through on commitments, and adapt to changing circumstances.
2. **Self-awareness** – A person can recognize his/her own emotions and how they affect their thoughts and behavior. A person knows his/her strengths and weaknesses, and has self-

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confidence.

3. **Social awareness** – A person has empathy and can understand the emotions, needs, and concerns of other people, pick up on emotional cues, feel comfortable socially, and recognize the power dynamics in a group or organization.
4. **Relationship management** – A person knows how to develop and maintain good relationships, communicate clearly, inspire and influence others, work well in a team, and manage conflict.

The academic performance is defined by students’ reporting of past semester CGPA/GPA and their expected GPA for the current semester. The grade point average or GPA is now used by most of the tertiary institutions as a convenient summary measure of the **academic performance** of their students. The GPA is a better measurement because it provides a greater insight into the relative level of **performance** of individuals and different group of students.

Academic Performance is an extent to which a student, a teacher or an institution has achieved their short- or long-term educational goals.

Academic performance is measured by the final grade earned in the course.

1.1.0 Need for the study:

Emotional Intelligence affects Performance at School or Work:

High emotional intelligence can help a person navigate the social complexities of the workplace, lead and motivate others, and excel in their career.

1.2.0 statement of the Problem: A Correlative Study of Emotional Intelligence and Academic Performance of the Teacher Trainees

1.3.0 Operational definitions of the terms:

Emotional Intelligence: is the ability to understand, use, and manage your own emotions in positive ways to relieve stress, communicate effectively, empathize with others, overcome challenges and defuse conflict.

Academic Performance is an extent to which a student, a teacher or an institution has achieved their short- or long-term educational goals.

Teacher Trainees: Teacher trainees are the students who are studying in the teacher training courses i.e. J.B.T., B.Ed., and M.Ed. In the present study the term teacher trainees’ stands for the pupil teachers of the B.Ed. Course.

1.4.0 Objectives of the study

1. To study the present status of Emotional Intelligence of Teacher Trainees.
2. To study whether there exists any significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of Teacher Trainees based on their Locality.
3. To study whether there exists any significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of Science and Arts stream of Teacher Trainees
4. To study whether there exists any significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Performance of Teacher Trainees.

1.5.0 Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Teacher Trainees based on their Locality.
2. There is no significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of Science and Arts Teacher Trainees.
3. There is no significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Performance of Teacher Trainees.

1.6.0 Methodology

The present study was a descriptive survey study. In order to meet the objectives of the study, the investigator had selected the two variables namely Emotional Intelligence and Academic Performance.

1.6.1 Population: The population for the study includes all the Teacher Trainees of D.K district.

1.6.2 Sample: The sample consisted of 52 Teacher Trainees from College of Education, Srinivas University, Mangaluru taluk.

1.7.0 Tool: Emotional Intelligence inventory was developed by Dr. S.K. Mangal and Mrs. Shubhra Mangal. In this inventory there are total 100 items and it is divided into four areas (Intra-personal management, interpersonal management, intrapersonal awareness and interpersonal awareness)

1.8.0 Statistical Techniques used: Mean, Standard Deviation, ‘t’-test and Pearson’s product movement coefficient of correlation methods were used for data analysis to measure the

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Emotional Intelligence and its Relation between Academic Performance among the Teacher Trainees.

1.9 Analysis of the objectives

1.9.1: Analysis of objective One - The first objective was to study the present status of Emotional Intelligence of Teacher Trainees of Mangaluru taluk.

The following table shows the frequencies of the scores of the present status of Emotional Intelligence of Teacher Trainees

Table1.1: showing the frequencies of the scores of the present status of Emotional Intelligence of Teacher Trainees:

Levels	Number of teacher trainees	The present status of Emotional Intelligence in percentage
High	11	21%
Average	33	64%
Low	8	15%

Figure1.1: Pie chart showing the percentages of frequencies of scores of the present status of Emotional Intelligence of Teacher Trainees

The Table 1.1 and Figure 1.1 reveals that 64% of teacher trainees have moderate or average level of Emotional Intelligence, 21% of students have high level of Emotional Intelligence, 15% of students have low level of Emotional Intelligence.

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1.9.2 Analysis of objective Two - To study whether there exists any significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of Teacher Trainees based on their Locality.

The following table shows the frequencies of any significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of Teacher Trainees based on their Locality.

Table 1.2: Number (N), Mean (M), Standard Deviation (S.D), and ‘t’ value of the scores of Emotional Intelligence of based on the Locality of teacher trainees

Locality	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Significance
Urban	26	66.64	9.214481	4.29	Significant
Rural	26	58.88	7.446028		

The Table 1.2 reveals that ‘t’ value is 4.29 which is significant. Hence, the null hypothesis “There a significant difference in the scores of Emotional Intelligence of teacher trainees based on their Locality” is rejected and research hypothesis is accepted. The mean of urban teacher trainees is 66.64 which is higher than the rural teacher trainees which is 58.88. It can be interpreted that urban teacher trainees have higher emotional intelligence than the rural teacher trainees.

1.9.3 Analysis of objective Three - To study whether there exists any significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of Science and Arts Teacher Trainees of Mangaluru taluk.

The following table shows the frequencies of any significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of Science and Arts Teacher Trainees.

Table 1.3: Number (N), Mean (M), Standard Deviation (S.D), and ‘t’ value of significant difference in the level of Emotional Intelligence of Science and Arts Teacher Trainees.

Stream	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Significance
Science	20	66.25	9.791914	2.72	Significant
Arts	32	61.125	7.6453		

The Table 1.3 reveals that ‘t’ value is 2.72 which is significant. Hence, the null hypothesis “There is a difference between Emotional Intelligence of Science and Arts teacher trainees” is rejected and research hypothesis is accepted. From the study, it can be interpreted that the Teacher Trainees from Science stream have higher emotional intelligence than the Teacher Trainees from Arts stream.

1.9.4 Analysis of objective Four- To study whether there exists any significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance of teacher trainees of Mangaluru taluk

The following table shows the frequencies of any significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Performance of Teacher Trainees.

Table 1.4: Number (N), Mean (M), Standard Deviation (S.D), and ‘R’ value of any significant difference in the level of the relation between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Performance of Teacher Trainees.

Stream	N	Mean	SD	‘R’ value	Significance
Emotional Intelligence	52	63.09615	9.381374	0.285	Significant
Academic Performance	52	78.0962	7.20637		

The Table 1.4 reveals that ‘R’ value is 0.285 which is significant. Hence, the null hypothesis “There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance of teacher trainees” is rejected and research hypothesis is accepted. It can be interpreted that there is a relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Performance. Higher the emotional intelligence, higher would be the academic performance.

Major Findings of the study

1. The study on present status of Emotional Intelligence of Teacher Trainees reveal that 21% of students fall under high level of Emotional Intelligence, 64% under average and 15% of students fall under low level of Emotional Intelligence.
2. The study shows that there is a significant difference in the scores of Emotional Intelligence of based on the Locality of Teacher Trainees. It can be interpreted that urban teacher trainees have higher emotional intelligence than the rural teacher trainees.
3. From the study it reveals that there is a difference between Emotional Intelligence of Teacher Trainees from Science and Arts Stream. It can be interpreted that the Teacher Trainees from Science stream have higher emotional intelligence than the Teacher Trainees from Arts stream.
4. The result reveals that there is relationship between academic achievement and emotional

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intelligence. Higher the emotional intelligence, higher would be the academic performance.

1.10.0 Educational implications of the study:

The result of the study can be usefully employed in College of Education. The present study has the following educational implications for the student teachers:

- g. Training programmes can be conducted to improve the communication skills of the Student Teachers of rural Area.
- h. Guidance can be given to the student teachers from Arts stream by an in-house education counsellor to enhance their emotional intelligence.
- i. Talks by Experts could be organised to the student teachers from rural on various topics.
- j. The group discussions and debates can be organised to boost the confidence level of the student teachers from rural area there by improving their overall performance level.
- k. Different co-curricular activities can be conducted to improve the team spirit among the teacher trainees from Arts stream.

1.11.0 Limitations of the study

- g. If the study was conducted on teacher trainees from different Colleges of Education of Mangaluru, would have given wider scope of study.
- h. If the study was applied on a large sample of teacher trainees of rural and urban localities, would have resulted in more accurate results.

1.12.0 Conclusion

The study reveals that there is a relationship between emotional intelligence and the academic performance with respect to the student teachers background in terms of their locality and stream of study (Science/Arts).

References:

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